

A Comparative Assessment of Constraints in the Utilization of Custom Hiring Centres in Haryana State

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The study was conducted in 2024 to enhance access to farm mechanization through Custom Hiring Centres in Haryana. A total of 200 respondents (120 farmers & 80 office bearers) from four purposively selected districts, namely Kaithal, Jind, Fatehabad and Sirsa, were chosen to collect data. Simple random sampling was employed in the selection of blocks, custom hiring centres and respondents. The results indicated that respondents facing socio-personal, economic, and technical constraints, viz., communication gaps among farmers, higher initial investment in machinery, and the non-availability of farm machinery during peak season, were very serious constraints for farmers. Whereas the non-return of machinery in a timely manner, seasonal demands, and lack of access to spare parts and support services are constraints faced by office bearers of custom hiring centres. Hence, extension efforts need to be strengthened to create awareness among the farming community about the effectiveness of CHCs.

Keywords: Custom hiring centres, constraints, utilization, farm mechanization, farmers

Custom Hiring Centres (CHCs) are units that comprise farm machinery, implements, and equipment for custom hiring by farmers (Rao et al., 2023). India is a predominantly agricultural country and 47 per cent of the population depends on it for their livelihood (PIB, 2023). The average operational land holding is estimated at 1.16 hectares and nearly 86.08 per cent of the land holdings are operated by marginal and small farmers owning less than 1 and 1-2 hectares, respectively (Government of India, 2021). Farm mechanization is thought to have decreased the cost of human labor by 20%, animal labor by 60%, and seeds and fertilizers by 15%. In wheat crops, automation led to a 10% increase in output, a 25% decrease in seed costs, a 30% decrease in irrigation water costs, and time savings for farm managers (Prasad et al., 2014). The prevalence of small farms in India and the technical and financial viability of using machinery result in relevant constraints. As a result, there is a need to design technologies that are appropriate and scale-specific.

The availability of land, labor, and capital is crucial to agriculture,

with labor being one of the most crucial inputs in farm operations. Lack of agricultural labour is one of the main problems faced by Indian farmers in rural areas (Kadaraiah et al., 2022). The increase in labour costs has made it harder for farmers to get fair prices for their produce. By reducing input costs, reducing drudgery, and enabling the timely completion of farm operations, agricultural mechanization plays a vital role in increasing agricultural output. Mechanization remains out of reach for many marginal and small farmers nationwide, although it is typically found among farmers with large operating holdings. One of the main obstacles to agricultural production has been identified as the lack of farm machinery, particularly for marginal and small farmers (Ghanghas et al., 2024). Before the SMAM (Sub-Mission on Agricultural Mechanization) program was implemented, the average Farm Power Availability in India was 1.84 kW/ha. Farm power of 2.5 kW/ha by 2022 and 4.00 kW/ha by 2030 is considered essential to achieving the necessary production intensity and cropping average (Final Report on M&E SMAM, 2018). One of the main obstacles to the growth of agriculture and the rise in its production and productivity is the lack of farm equipment and power, particularly for farmers with modest land holdings. The problem of low productivity can be addressed by expanding access to high-end farm equipment for small and marginal farmers. The majority of farmers in the nation, however, are unable to purchase costly farm equipment; as a result, they may turn to custom hiring centres for machinery on a rental basis (Kisku & Bisht, 2022).

The government of Haryana has established 6,755 custom hiring service centres from 2018-19 to 2022-23 under the scheme entitled "Promotion of Agricultural Mechanization for In-Situ Management of Crop Residue in Punjab, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh and NCT of Delhi". The burning of paddy straw here poses a significant environmental challenge. The special thing is that these CHCs are playing a pivotal role in managing Parali (Government of Haryana, 2021). Due to the high cost of farm machinery and the fragmented nature of agricultural land held predominantly by small and marginal farmers, mechanization becomes challenging. By utilizing the

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services of custom hiring centres, small and marginal farmers can access a range of agricultural implements to increase crop production and productivity, without investing in their purchase. The development of custom hiring mechanisms not only improves access to machinery for small and marginal farmers but also provides better services to farmers. Because the intensive cropping pattern necessitates the highest level of mechanization to guarantee food security, ecological and environmental safety, farmers' economic security, etc., it was deemed necessary to look at the custom hiring centres' service utilization patterns and determine the constraints that farmers face when using these services.

Method

Participants

The present study was carried out in four districts of Haryana, namely Sirsa, Fatehabad, Kaithal and Jind. These districts were purposively selected due to the highest concentration of Custom Hiring Centres (CHCs). From each selected district, two blocks were chosen through random sampling, resulting in a total of eight blocks. Further, five Custom Hiring Centres were randomly selected from each block. From every selected CHC, two office bearers and three beneficiary farmers were chosen using simple random sampling for personal interviews. In this manner, a total sample of 200 respondents was constituted, comprising 80 CHC office bearers and 120 beneficiary farmers.

Measure

The constraints encountered by the respondents were categorized into three major groups: socio-personal, economic and technical constraints. Data were collected using a structured interview schedule, and responses were recorded on a three-point continuum indicating the severity of each constraint, namely very serious,

serious and not so serious.

To quantify the severity of constraints, the Weighted Mean Score (WMS) was calculated for each item by dividing the total weighted score by the total number of respondents. The constraints were then ranked based on their respective WMS values. Further, respondents were classified into three categories according to the overall degree of constraints faced, using mean and standard deviation as the basis for classification.

Analysis

To examine differences in the degree of constraints experienced by beneficiary farmers and CHC office bearers, an independent-samples t-test was applied. This statistical test was employed to determine whether any significant difference existed between the two groups with respect to the constraints encountered.

Results

The results presented in Table 1 reveal that farmers faced several constraints in the utilization of Custom Hiring Centres (CHCs). Among the socio-personal constraints, the communication gap among farmers in sharing CHC-related information was ranked first, followed by limited awareness about machinery available at CHCs, while cultural incompatibility was the least severe constraint. Regarding economic constraints, higher initial investment in machinery and implements emerged as the most severe constraint, followed by higher production cost compared to the conventional method, whereas overlapping of farm operations and high transportation costs were perceived as less severe constraints. Under technical constraints, non-availability of farm machinery during the peak season was ranked first followed by lack of extension support. Insufficient variety of machinery and implements ranked third, while the tedious procedure followed to avail CHC services was perceived as the least important technical constraint.

Table 1
Constraints Faced by the Farmers in the Utilization of CHCs (n=120)

S. no.	Constraints	TWS	WMS	Rank
I	Socio-Personal Constraints			
1	Inability to take risks	254	2.11	3
2	Cultural incompatibility	220	1.83	5
3	Fragmented land holding	244	2.03	4
4	Limited awareness about the machinery at CHCs	284	2.36	2
5	Communication gap among farmers (in sharing CHC's information)	308	2.56	1
II	Economic Constraints			
1	Overlapping of farm operations	253	2.10	5
2	High hiring charges	322	2.68	3
3	Inadequate financial support from the government	319	2.65	4
4	High transportation costs	228	1.90	6
5	Higher initial investment in machinery and implements	343	2.85	1
6	Higher production cost than the conventional method	339	2.82	2
III	Technical Constraints			
1	Lack of training on CHC	253	2.10	4
2	Lack of extension support	284	2.36	2
3	Lack of digital integration in CHC	250	2.08	5
4	Insufficient variety of machinery & implements	275	2.29	3
5	Non-availability of farm machinery during peak season	291	2.42	1
6	A tedious procedure was followed to avail the services of CHC	245	2.04	6

Note. TWS= total weighted score, WMS= weighted mean score

The data in Table 2 show that, among socio-personal constraints, the non-return of machinery safely and on time was the most severe constraint faced by office bearers of CHCs, followed by the inability to take risks, while issues related to trust and relationship management with farmers were perceived as the least severe constraints. Regarding economic constraints, seasonal demand was ranked the most important, followed by high initial capital investment. High maintenance and repair costs and cumbersome

bank loans with high interest rates were perceived as the least important economic constraints. Under technical constraints, limited access to spare parts and support services emerged as the most severe constraint, followed by a complex procedure to obtain approval for a CHC. Compatibility and customization of farm machinery ranked third, while the lack of extension and digital integration support in CHCs was perceived as a less severe constraint faced by office bearers of CHCs.

Table 2

Constraints Faced by the Office Bearer in the Utilization of CHC (n=80)

S. no.	Constraints	TWS	WMS	Rank
I	Socio-Personal Constraints			
1	Inability to take risks	181	2.26	2
2	Cultural incompatibility	174	2.17	4
3	Non-return of machinery safely and on time	195	2.43	1
4	Trust and relationship management with farmers	166	2.07	5
5	Limited access to knowledge and skill development	177	2.21	3
II	Economic Constraints			
1	Seasonal demand	234	1.95	1
2	High initial capital investment	230	1.91	2
3	High maintenance & repair costs	178	1.48	5
4	A cumbersome bank loan with high interest rates	170	1.41	6
5	Payment problem	219	1.82	3
6	Inadequate subsidies	217	1.80	4
III	Technical Constraints			
1	Lack of training on CHC	222	2.77	4
2	Lack of extension support	182	2.27	5
3	Lack of digital integration in CHC	175	2.18	6
4	Complex procedure to get approval of a CHC	234	2.92	2
5	Limited access to spare parts & support services	239	2.98	1
6	Compatibility & customization of farm machinery	223	2.78	3

Note. TWS= total weighted score, WMS= weighted mean score

The data in Table 3 reveal that economic constraints were the biggest barriers to the utilization of CHCs by farmers, while technical constraints were the least. For the office bearers, technical

constraints were the biggest hurdle to the use of CHCs, while socio-personal constraints were the least serious.

Table 3

Major Constraints Faced by Farmers and Office Bearers in the Utilization of CHCs

S. no.	Constraint category	WMS (f)	Rank (f)	WMS (OB)	Rank (OB)
1	Socio-Personal Constraints	2.18	2	2.23	3
2	Economic Constraints	2.50	1	2.60	2
3	Technical Constraints	2.21	3	2.65	1

Comparison of Constraints Faced by Respondents in the Utilization of CHCs

The results from the independent sample t-test presented in the Table 4 indicated that there was no significant difference in the degree of socio-personal and economic constraints faced by the respondents in

the utilization of custom hiring centres, whereas, for technical constraints, the t-value is significant at 0.01 level of significance which signifies a significant mean difference between the respondents (farmers & office bearers of CHCs). It can be observed that the office bearers face a higher degree of technical constraints than farmers.

Table 4*Comparison of Constraints Faced by Farmers and Office Bearers of CHCs (f=120), (OB=80)*

S. no.	Constraint category	Mean (f)	SD (f)	Mean (OB)	SD (OB)	Mean difference	t-value
1	Socio-Personal Constraints	2.18	0.41	2.23	0.58	0.05	0.344 ^{NS}
2	Economic Constraints	2.50	0.69	2.60	0.81	0.10	0.720 ^{NS}
3	Technical Constraints	2.21	0.54	2.65	0.91	0.44	4.213 ^{**}

Note. NS= non-significant, **= Significant at 0.01 level of significance, f= farmer, OB= office bearer, SD= standard deviation

Discussion

The findings of the study show that there is a considerable difference among types of constraints faced by the two groups of respondents, i.e., farmers and office bearers of custom hiring centres. Economic constraints were the biggest hurdle for the former type of respondents. This could be attributed to the higher initial investment in machinery and the higher production costs compared with conventional farming methods. This finding reflects the limited financial capacity of most farmers, particularly small and marginal farmers, who often find large capital investments in farm machinery unaffordable. The high purchase cost, coupled with low and seasonal utilization of machinery, discourages individual ownership and increases perceived financial risk. The findings are in line with (Parashunath et al., 2016; & Kisku et al., 2022). Furthermore, technical constraints were the biggest barriers faced by the office bearers of the CHCs, as the findings revealed that inadequate availability of spare parts and after-sales support, particularly in rural areas, results in frequent machinery breakdowns and extended idle periods, adversely affecting service continuity and revenue generation. The absence of localized service centres and skilled technicians further increases maintenance time and operational costs, thereby reducing the overall efficiency of CHCs. The findings are supported by Nissa et al. (2017), Agrawal et al. (2020), Kisku et al. (2022), Roy et al. (2022), and Ghanghas et al. (2024).

The findings reveal that socio-personal constraints were perceived at nearly the same level by both groups of respondents. The mean difference (0.05) was statistically non-significant ($t = 0.344$), indicating a common understanding among both groups regarding socio-personal issues such as cooperation, awareness, and interpersonal relations associated with CHC functioning. Similarly, office bearers perceived economic constraints marginally higher than farmers. However, the observed mean difference of 0.10 was also non-significant ($t = 0.720$), suggesting that both farmers and office bearers faced comparable economic challenges- such as high operational costs, limited financial support, and maintenance expenses. In contrast, a statistically significant difference was observed in the perception of technical constraints. Office bearers reported considerably higher technical constraints than farmers, with a mean difference of 0.44, which was significant at the 0.01 level ($t = 4.213$). This indicates that office bearers, being directly involved in the management and operation of CHCs, were more affected by technical issues such as machinery breakdowns, lack of skilled operators, difficulties in repair and maintenance, and inadequate technical training. Farmers, on the other hand, may have perceived these constraints to a lesser extent, as their interaction with technical aspects is relatively limited to machinery use. The findings are backed by Roy et al. (2022) and Kisku et al. (2022).

Conclusion

The study concludes that the communication gap among farmers, higher initial investment in machinery and non-availability of farm machinery during peak season were very serious constraints faced by the farmers. Similarly, non-return of machinery in a timely manner, seasonal demand, and lack of access to spare parts were the biggest hurdles faced by office bearers in the utilization of CHCs. There is a considerable difference in the types of constraints faced by farmers and office bearers of custom hiring centres due to variations in extension support, training, and awareness. The study recommends that high-power multi-operation big machinery may be replaced by the development of low-power single-operation small machinery, thereby reducing initial costs for promoting CHCs. Enhancement in individual subsidies as well as timely full release in spite of instalments as suggested by CHC, owners. Besides these, they also suggested allowing open-market purchases of machinery to improve quality and address concerns about machinery quality.

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